

1 **FIBP, a molecule with decoy properties in growth factor signaling.**

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7 FIBP affected nutritional sensing through MLST8 and TBCB. A number of genes functioning in cell death
8 were top targets of FIBP regulation including UBR7, UBA1, and BAD. A novel pathway of growth factor
9 signaling control through FIBP appeared to occur through DR1-associated DRAP1 which functions in
10 cytosolic arginine sensing by mTORC1.

11 Citations

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